

CHET TILI FANLARINI O‘QITISHDA INNOVATSIYALAR: IJODIY
JAMOA METODI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada chet tili darslarida innovativ metodlardan, xususan, ijodiy jamoa metodidan foydalanish orqali o‘quvchilarning ijodkorlik hamda mustaqil fikrlash qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: metod, innovativ, ijodkorlik, mustaqil fikrlash, ijodiy jamoa, faoliyat, taqdimot, hamkorlikda ishlash.

Bugungi kun chet tili fani o‘qituvchisidan o‘z o‘quvchilariga xorijiy tilni o‘rgatishda chuqur bilim va katta mahorat talab etiladi. O‘quvchilar bilim, ko‘nikma va malakalarida ijobiy natijaga erishish borasida har bir dars jarayonida vaqt taqsimoti, o‘qituvchi va o‘quvchi faoliyatini to‘g‘ri tashkil qilish muhim omil hisoblanadi. Ilg‘or mahalliy va xorijiy tajribalardan foydalanib darslarda yangi innovatsion metodlarni qo‘llashda chet tili fani o‘qituvchisi o‘tilayotgan mavzular va ularning mazmuni o‘quvchilarning yosh xususiyatlari va psixologiyasiga mos kelishi, fanlararo bog‘likligi hamda izchilligiga e’tibor qaratishi lozim.

Xorijiy til fanlarini o‘qitishda “Communicative Language Teaching”(CLT), “Case-study”, “Self-assessment” kabi innovativ metodlar o‘quvchilarning og‘zaki nutqini o‘stirishda, jamoa bo‘lib ishlashda va o‘z-o‘zini baholashda keng qo‘llanilayotgan metodlar jumlasiga kiradi. Ammo bulardan farqli o‘laroq “**Ijodiy jamoa**” metodi nafaqat og‘zaki nutqni o‘stirish va hamkorlikda ishlash, balki ijodkorlik hamda mustaqil fikrlash qobiliyatlarini ham shakllantirishda ham katta ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Ushbu metodning “**Case-study**” metodidan farqi shundaki, har bir ijodiy jamoa kichik taqdimoti orqali boshqa jamoalarni faollashtiruvchi biron ijodiy topshiriq o‘ylab topib bajartirishidir. O‘quvchilar $\frac{3}{4}$ qatnashchidan iborat alohida “**Ijodiy jamoa**” guruhlariga bo‘linadi va har biri o‘z jamoa a‘zolari bilan biron bir qiziqarli faoliyatni amalga oshiradilar: Misol uchun “Watching TV – is it good?” mavzusida ushbu metoddan foydalanish jarayonida har bir ijodiy jamoa o‘zlari boshlovchi sifatida, qolgan jamoa vakillarini ishtirokchilar sifatida qatnashtirib, kichik “studiya” tashkil qilishgan holda biron qiziqarli o‘yin, topishmoq yoki crosswordlardan foydalanib, shou o‘tkazib berishlari mumkin bo‘ladi. Aniqroq qilib aytganda, ushbu metod ikki bosqichda amalga oshiriladi:

1. **Sinfdan tashqari ish.** Bu jarayonda o‘quvchilar darsdan tashqari vaqtda o‘qituvchi yordamida berilgan mavzu yuzasidan 5-7 daqiqalik ijodiy topshiriqlar tayyorlaydilar.

2. **Jamoa bo‘lib ishlash.** Bu jarayon dars davomida amalga oshiriladi.

Amaliyotda 7-sinf ingliz tili fanidan “Homereading: Kevin’s holidays” mavzusiga oid ijodiy jamoalar faoliyatlarini misol tariqasida keltiramiz.

Metod: Ijodiy jamoa - Creative Team Method.

Group 1. Translate and match. (This task is prepared as a matching activity.)

Suddenly - to‘satdan, free like a bird - erkin qushdek, a doorbell - eshik qo‘ng‘irog‘i, stamp collection – markalar kolleksiyasi, be angry-jahli chiqmoq, make a mistake - xato qilmoq.

Group 2. Read and put in correct order.

a) The next day was even worse for him. Everything good in the morning and in the afternoon. Something bad happened in the evening. It all started when Max put dirty clothes in the washing machine. After sometime Kevin heard some strange sounds from the washing machine. He went to look at it and found that Max put his best pair of shoes into the machine with the clothes.

b) One day Kevin was reading the newspaper when he saw interesting news. He read it aloud. “Last week someone stole Dick Brown’s stamps”. Dick Brown

was famous all over the world for his stamp collection. They were very expensive. Some more people lost their stamp collections too. The police were looking for them.

c) It was his cousin Max. “Hiii!”, cried Max and started jumping on Kevin’s bed, breaking his crayons into the parts “I have come to stay here for the holidays”. Kevin was not happy to have such a “surprise” for his holidays. Max was Kevin’s pain. He was always doing things wrong. So the next holidays will be the worst in his life. The next few days were horrible for Kevin. After breakfast Kevin decided to do a painting. Luckily, Max was not at home. Kevin took out all his art things and started painting a beautiful picture. When he was finishing his picture, Max entered the room with a Pepsi bottle. He poured Pepsi all over the painting, and the picture became bad.

d) People who had stamps afraid to lose their collections. Kevin had a nice stamp collection and it was with his friend Allan. He decided to get his stamp album back. But Kevin could not go out because his mother’s friend came to see them and her mother wanted to be at home. Kevin decided to send Max to get his album. Kevin gave Max Allan’s address, and Max left the house. Max soon came back with the album, and when Kevin looked at it he found out it was not his album. The stamps were very expensive.

e) Kevin was waiting for his holidays. His mother said about a big surprise for him during holidays. Summer holidays started. Now he was free like a bird. Free to draw, paint, play cricket and watch Television ... anything he wanted to do. Kevin took out his crayons and the album. He’s going to draw a picture when suddenly the doorbell rang.

f) Max lost his way and went to another house by mistake. The door was open but there were no people at home. The album was on the table. So Max went in and found an album. He took it and brought to Kevin. Kevin thought that it was Dick Brown’s album. Kevin called the police and told that he found a stamp album. A week later Kevin and Max got good prizes for finding Dick Brown’s album. “I will

never be angry at Max” Kevin thought. “Kevin, I was jumping on the sofa and I broke your glasses. Anybody can make a mistake”, said Max.

Check your answers: 1.e 2. c 3.a 4. b 5.d 6.f

Group 3. Write the sentences .

1.was waiting/ for his holidays. /Kevin . 2.a Pepsi bottle./ his picture,/ Max entered /the room with / When /he /was finishing. 3.It / in the washing machine./all started/ when /put /dirty clothes / Max. 4.Kevin / friend Allan./ and /it was/ with his / had /a nice stamp collection. ...

Check your answers:

1. Kevin was waiting for his holidays. 2.When he was finishing his picture, Max entered the room with a Pepsi bottle. 3.It all started when Max put dirty clothes in the washing machine. 4.Kevin had a nice stamp collection and it was with his friend Allan. ...

Group 4. Test your knowledge.

1. What does Kevin do on summer holidays?

A. visit his grandparents B. go to the camping

C.anything what he wanted to do: read books, play cricket, draw, paint...

2. What was a “surprise”?

A.Dick Brown’s collection B. Max has come to stay for the holidays

C. Allan has come to stay for the holidays

3.What do you think: why Max was Kevin’s pain?

A . He was always doing things wrong. B .He helped Kevin to do homework.

C .He always did all his works accurately.

4. Is Kevin angry at Max? Why?

A .Yes, because he was always doing things wrong.

B .No, because he helped to find Dick Brown's collection and they became prize.

C . No, because helped to find Allan's collection and they became prize. ...

Topshiriqlar va faoliyatlar ko'lamini o'qituvchi mahoratiga ko'ra turlicha bo'lishi mumkin: og'zaki savol-javob, tinglab tushunish, xatolarni topish, o'qib tushunish, mimikali yoki harakatli o'yinlar, gaplarni davom qildirish, savollar tuzish, gap zamonlarini o'zgartirish, topishmoqlar, crosswordlar...

Xulosa shuki, "**ijodiy jamoa**" metodidan foydalanish jarayonida o'quvchilar til materialini avvalo o'zi puxta tushunib o'rganib oladi. So'ngra yangilik yaratishga intiladi, ijodiy izlanadi, o'ziga va jamoadoshlariga nisbatan ishonch va talabchanlik hissi ortadi.

Adabiyotlar:

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